

Green Technology and Talent Management: Nurturing Sustainability in the Workforce

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Abstract

Sustainable development, reducing adverse environmental effects, and fostering economic viability over the long term all need green technology and talent management. To demonstrate the need to incorporate environmentally responsible practices into organizational plans, this talk investigates the convergence of green technology and talent management. At the beginning of the presentation, there is a general overview of green technology, which includes the many forms of green technology and its advantages. Next, it dives into talent management's role in encouraging the adoption of environmentally friendly technologies, highlighting the necessity of locating, cultivating, and retaining skilled persons capable of contributing to sustainable environmental development. Case studies highlight the successful deployment of environmentally friendly technology through efficient people management, the problems encountered, and the lessons learned. This article covers the best practices for combining green technology with personnel management. These practices include aligning organizational goals with green efforts, developing a culture of sustainability, and utilizing technology for talent management through green practices. Emerging technologies and the changing role of talent management in promoting innovation and sustainability are showcased in this article, which also delves into the future trends and opportunities in green technology and talent management. To create a sustainable future, the presentation ends with a call to action for enterprises to adopt environmentally friendly practices and invest in developing their personnel.

Keywords: *green technology, talent management, sustainability*